

ENTREPRENEURIAL RESILIENCE IN ANHUI: EXPLORING STIMULATION AND PROTECTION AMIDST THE "THREE REGIONS AND ONE DISTRICT" PARADIGM

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Abstract

Anhui Province, positioned as a pivotal province within the central region of China, has embarked on an ambitious trajectory of development, epitomized by the concerted efforts towards the construction of the "three regions and one district" framework. This strategic initiative delineates Anhui's vision to emerge as a crucial nexus for integrated development within the Yangtze River Delta, a burgeoning hub for inland economic expansion, a bastion of ecological civilization, and a crucible for industrial innovation and advancement. At its core, this strategic endeavor not only underscores the imperative for propelling Anhui's economic growth towards high-quality benchmarks but also seeks to cultivate novel drivers and galvanize the impetus for societal innovation. Within this transformative landscape, entrepreneurship emerges as a linchpin force in propelling social and economic advancement, assuming a paramount role in catalyzing innovation and safeguarding its flourishing. Positioned at the vanguard of entrepreneurial dynamics, Anhui province is poised to harness the potential of entrepreneurial endeavors as potent instruments for driving economic dynamism and fostering societal resilience. By fostering an ecosystem conducive to entrepreneurship, Anhui endeavors to unlock new avenues for economic diversification, spur job creation, and nurture a culture of innovation and creativity.

1. Introduction

As an important province in the central region of China, Anhui Province has actively promoted the construction of "three regions and one region" in recent years, that is, to build an important strategic fulcrum for the integrated development of the Yangtze River Delta, a new highland of inland opening up, a model area for ecological civilization construction and a demonstration area for industrial innovation and development. This major strategy not only aims to promote the high-quality economic development of Anhui province, but also aims to cultivate new drivers and stimulate the vitality of social innovation. In this context, entrepreneurship, as an important force

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to promote social and economic development, is particularly important to stimulate and protect it. Entrepreneurship, reflected in the characteristics of innovation, adventure, cooperation and continuous learning, is a key factor in promoting social progress and economic development^[1]. In the process of the construction of "three regions and one region" in Anhui province, how to effectively stimulate and protect the entrepreneurship is not only related to the survival and development of enterprises, but also affects the vitality and competitiveness of the whole regional economy. Therefore, it is of great significance to explore the well-inspiring mechanism of entrepreneurship under the background of "three regions and one district" to promote the high-quality economic development of Anhui province and even the whole Yangtze River Delta region. With the deepening of the construction of "three places and one area", Anhui will certainly face more opportunities and challenges. At this point, the development of entrepreneurship will become the key to meet these challenges and seize the opportunities. Through the systematic study of the stimulation and protection path of entrepreneurship, it can provide more powerful policy support and social environmental protection for entrepreneurs, and then promote the sustainable and healthy development of Anhui economy. At the same time, it will also provide a useful reference for other regions and promote the vigorous development of entrepreneurship nationwide^[2].

2. The influence of the construction of "Three Regions and one District" in Anhui province on entrepreneurship

The construction of "three regions and one district" in Anhui province has a multifaceted and far-reaching influence on entrepreneurship. First of all, from the perspective of policy environment, the construction of "three regions and one district" has provided strong support for the cultivation and development of entrepreneurship. The Anhui provincial government has issued a series of preferential policies, including tax incentives, financial support, land supply, etc., to attract and encourage more entrepreneurs to invest and start businesses in Anhui. The implementation of these policies has lowered the threshold and risks for entrepreneurs to start businesses, and stimulated their entrepreneurial enthusiasm and innovation vitality. At the same time, the government has also intensified the introduction and training of innovative and entrepreneurial talents, providing a talent guarantee for the inheritance and development of entrepreneurship. Secondly, the influence of regional economic development on entrepreneurship cannot be ignored. With the promotion of the construction of "three regions and one district", the economic strength of Anhui Province has been continuously improved, and the industrial structure has been continuously optimized, providing a broader market and more development opportunities for entrepreneurs^[3]. In such an economic environment, entrepreneurs are more sensitive to capture market opportunities and face market challenges more confidently, thus showing a more positive and innovative entrepreneurial spirit. In addition, the impact of the social-cultural environment on entrepreneurship is equally important. Anhui province has a long history and profound cultural deposits. This unique cultural atmosphere provides a rich soil for the breeding of entrepreneurship. In Anhui province, the social fashion of respecting innovation and encouraging entrepreneurship is increasingly popular, which has created a good social environment for the stimulation and protection of entrepreneurship. At the same time, with the general improvement of education level and the in-depth development of innovation and entrepreneurship education, more and more people begin to have entrepreneurial awareness and innovation ability, which has laid a solid social foundation for the inheritance and development of entrepreneurship. To sum up, the construction of "three regions and one district" has had a positive and far-reaching impact on entrepreneurship by optimizing the policy environment, promoting regional economic development, and shaping a good social and cultural environment. These influences are not only reflected in the stimulation and protection of the existing entrepreneurship, but also in the cultivation and inheritance of the future entrepreneurship. Therefore, the construction of "three places and

one district" is an important opportunity and strong support for Anhui province to cultivate and develop entrepreneurship^[4].

3. The key path to inspire entrepreneurship

The stimulation of entrepreneurship is an important driving force to promote the sustainable development of the construction of "three regions and one district" in Anhui province. Its key paths mainly include innovation and entrepreneurship education, the guidance of excellent entrepreneurs and the creation of a cultural atmosphere tolerant of failure^[5].

3.1 The deepening of innovation and entrepreneurship education

Innovation and entrepreneurship education is seen as the cornerstone of inspiring entrepreneurship. In Anhui province, from basic education to higher education, they are actively exploring the integration of innovation and entrepreneurship into the curriculum system. By opening entrepreneurship courses, organizing entrepreneurship practices, holding entrepreneurship competitions and other activities, students' entrepreneurial awareness and innovation ability are cultivated. In addition, the close cooperation between universities, research institutions and enterprises also provides a platform for students to apply theoretical knowledge to practice, helping them cultivate their problem-solving ability and teamwork spirit in practice. Not only that, Anhui also attaches great importance to the innovation and entrepreneurship training for social people. Through holding various entrepreneurship training classes, entrepreneurship salons and other activities, we will provide guidance and support to people who are willing to start their own businesses, and help them transform their entrepreneurial ideas into practical actions.

3.2 Leading by the example of outstanding entrepreneurs

The demonstration effect of successful entrepreneurs plays an important role in stimulating the entrepreneurial spirit. In Anhui, more and more outstanding entrepreneurs have emerged. They have become social role models with their keen market insight, excellent innovation ability and indomitable entrepreneurial spirit. Through media publicity, entrepreneur forums, entrepreneurship lectures and other ways, the experiences and stories of these successful entrepreneurs have been widely spread, encouraging more people to embark on the road of entrepreneurship. At the same time, Anhui also attaches great importance to the exchange and cooperation between entrepreneurs. Through the establishment of entrepreneurs' associations, chambers of commerce and other organizations, it provides a platform for entrepreneurs to learn from each other and exchange experience. Here, they can share the joy of success, and they can also jointly discuss and solve the problems encountered in the process of entrepreneurship, thus forming a positive entrepreneurial cultural atmosphere^[6].

3.3 Create a cultural atmosphere of tolerance for failure

In the process of entrepreneurship, failure is inevitable. However, in the construction of "three places and one district" in Anhui province, a cultural atmosphere of tolerating failure and encouraging attempts is being formed. This cultural atmosphere holds that failure is a stepping stone to success and what drives individuals and organizations forward. Therefore, for entrepreneurs, failure is not terrible, the important thing is to be able to learn from failure to stand up and move on. In order to create this cultural atmosphere, Anhui has adopted a series of measures. For example, the government has set up a business failure guarantee fund to provide certain financial assistance to help them through difficulties. At the same time, all sectors of society also actively advocate tolerance and understanding of failure, and encourage entrepreneurs to be brave and innovate. In this cultural atmosphere, more and more people dare to take risks and innovate, which has injected a steady stream of vitality into the construction of "three places and one district" in Anhui province.

4. The formation mechanism of entrepreneurship protection

The formation mechanism of entrepreneurship protection is an important guarantee to ensure that entrepreneurs get legitimate rights and interests and necessary support in the process of starting their own businesses. In the

construction of "three regions and one district" in Anhui province, the formation mechanism of entrepreneurship protection mainly includes the guarantee of laws and regulations, government support and services, and the participation of social organizations.

4.1 *Guarantee provided by laws and regulations*

The establishment of a sound legal and regulatory system is the basis of protecting entrepreneurship. Anhui province has constantly improved relevant laws and regulations to provide a comprehensive and effective legal guarantee for entrepreneurs. First of all, strengthen the protection of intellectual property rights, encourage enterprises to apply for patents, trademarks and other intellectual property rights, crack down on infringement, and protect their innovation achievements. Secondly, improve the company law, contract law and other commercial legal systems, standardize the market order, and protect the legitimate rights and interests of entrepreneurs. In addition, the publicity and popularization of laws and regulations related to the rights and interests of entrepreneurs should be strengthened to improve their legal awareness and ability to protect their rights^[8].

4.2 *Government support and services*

The government plays an important role in protecting entrepreneurship. By providing policy support and quality services, the Anhui provincial government reduces the risk of entrepreneurship and creates a good environment for the development of entrepreneurship. First of all, a series of policies to support entrepreneurship will be introduced, including fiscal subsidies, tax incentives, loan support, etc., to reduce the economic burden of entrepreneurs and encourage them to actively start businesses. Second, we should optimize government services, simplify the examination and approval process, improve work efficiency, and provide more convenient and efficient services for entrepreneurs. In addition, the government has also strengthened the cultivation and support of small and medium-sized enterprises to promote their growth into competitive market players^[9].

4.3 *Participation of social organizations*

Social organizations play an irreplaceable role in the protection of entrepreneurship. In the construction of "three regions and one district" in Anhui province, industry associations, chambers of commerce and other social organizations have actively participated in the protection of entrepreneurship and provided strong support for entrepreneurs. First of all, these social organizations hold training, seminars and other activities to improve the professional quality and management ability of entrepreneurs, and help them better cope with market challenges. Secondly, as a bridge and link between enterprises and the government, they actively reflect the demands and suggestions of entrepreneurs and promote the formulation and improvement of policies. In addition, social organizations can also provide professional services such as legal advice and financing assistance to help them solve practical problems.

In addition to the above measures, Anhui province also pays attention to play the role of public opinion supervision and public participation. Through media publicity and social supervision, we will strengthen the supervision and evaluation of the entrepreneurship protection work, and encourage relevant departments to respond to and solve the problems faced by entrepreneurs in a timely manner. At the same time, we will encourage the public to participate in the protection of entrepreneurship and create a favorable atmosphere for the whole society to pay close attention to and support the development of entrepreneurs^[10].

5. *Practical cases of entrepreneurship stimulation and protection in the construction of "Three Regions and one District" in Anhui province*

In the construction of "three regions and one district" in Anhui Province, the stimulation and protection of entrepreneurial spirit have been widely concerned and practiced. In order to demonstrate this practice process more specifically, we chose Hefei High-tech Industrial Development Zone (hereinafter referred to as "Hefei High-

tech Zone") as the case study object. As a well-known scientific and technological innovation and industrial agglomeration area in Anhui Province and even the whole country, Hefei High-tech Zone has achieved remarkable achievements in the stimulation and protection of entrepreneurship, providing a useful reference for other regions.

5.1 Practice and Achievements of Hefei High-tech Industrial Development Zone

5.1.1 Policy guidance and innovation atmosphere

Through a series of policy guidance, Hefei High-tech Zone has provided strong support for the stimulation of entrepreneurship. For example, for start-up technology enterprises, the high-tech zone provides preferential policies such as tax relief and rent subsidies, which reduce the threshold and risk of starting a business. At the same time, the high-tech zone has also established a sound technology financial system to provide financing support for start-up enterprises and solve the problem of capital shortage. In terms of creating an innovative atmosphere, Hefei High-tech Zone pays attention to industry-university-research cooperation and promotes the transformation of scientific research achievements. Through close cooperation with universities and scientific research institutions, it provides enterprises with a steady stream of technical support and talent reserve. In addition, the high-tech Zone has also held various innovation and entrepreneurship activities, such as entrepreneurship competitions and innovation forums, which have stimulated the enthusiasm of the whole society for innovation and entrepreneurship of the whole society.

5.1.2 Demonstration and training support for excellent entrepreneurs

In the Hefei High-tech Zone, a number of outstanding entrepreneurs have played an exemplary and leading role. These successful entrepreneurs provide valuable guidance and help for start-up entrepreneurs through their own experience sharing and mentoring. At the same time, the high-tech Zone has also established a training system for entrepreneurs, and regularly holds entrepreneurship training courses and lectures to improve the professional quality and management ability of entrepreneurs.

5.1.3 Forgive failure and encourage attempts

Hefei High-tech Zone advocates a cultural atmosphere of tolerance for failure and encourages entrepreneurs to make bold attempts and innovations. For entrepreneurs who fail, the high-tech zone provides re-entrepreneurship support and psychological counseling, so that they can learn from the failure and cheer themselves together. This attitude of tolerating failure and the spirit of encouraging attempt provide entrepreneurs with a broader space for innovation and development opportunities.

5.2 Practical results

Through the implementation of the above series of measures, Hefei High-tech Zone has achieved remarkable results in the stimulation and protection of entrepreneurship. First of all, there is a strong atmosphere of innovation and entrepreneurship, and a large number of start-ups are incubated and grown here. Secondly, the innovation ability and management ability of entrepreneurs have been improved, and the competitiveness and market influence of enterprises have been continuously enhanced. Finally, the cultural atmosphere of tolerance for failure has encouraged more entrepreneurs to try and innovate, injecting new vitality into the regional economic development^[11].

5.3 Case revelation

From the practice cases of Hefei High-tech Zone, we can extract the following enlightenment and significance for the stimulation and protection of entrepreneurship:

Policy guidance is the key to stimulating entrepreneurship. The government should formulate targeted policies and measures to reduce the threshold and risks of entrepreneurship, and provide a good entrepreneurial environment and support for entrepreneurs.

The exemplary and leading role of outstanding entrepreneurs cannot be ignored. The experience and stories of successful entrepreneurs can inspire more people to take the road of entrepreneurship and form a positive entrepreneurial culture atmosphere.

A culture of tolerance for failure is an important support for entrepreneurship. Society should encourage attempts and tolerate failure, provide psychological support and re-entrepreneurship opportunities for entrepreneurs, and stimulate their innovative spirit and entrepreneurial enthusiasm.

Diversified support system is an important guarantee to protect entrepreneurship. The government, social organizations and enterprises themselves should jointly build a diversified support system to provide all-round support and services for entrepreneurs.

To sum up, the stimulation and protection practice of Hefei High-tech Industrial Development Zone to entrepreneurship in the construction of "three regions and one district" provides us with valuable experience and inspiration. These practical experiences can not only help to promote the vigorous development of entrepreneurship in Anhui province and even the whole country, but also have a positive reference significance for the innovation and entrepreneurship work in other regions.

6. Conclusion

This study deeply discusses the stimulation and protection practice of entrepreneurship in the construction of "three places and one district" in Anhui province, and draws important conclusions. We recognize that entrepreneurship has a central role in promoting economic development, innovation and job creation. Policy, market and social environment have a significant impact on the stimulation of entrepreneurship. Although Anhui province has taken a series of measures to successfully stimulate entrepreneurship, it still faces challenges such as policy implementation and market environment. To this end, we put forward the following policy suggestions: first, the government should increase the policy support for start-ups, such as fiscal, tax and other preferential policies, to lower the threshold of entrepreneurship. And establish policy evaluation mechanisms to ensure the effectiveness of policies. The market mechanism should be improved to ensure fair competition. The government needs to strengthen market supervision, protect the rights and interests of entrepreneurs and their innovative achievements, and promote the construction of a social credit system to improve the credibility of entrepreneurs. We will actively cultivate and spread entrepreneurship, raise public awareness through education and training, encourage exchanges and cooperation among entrepreneurs, and build a diversified social support system, including industry associations, intermediaries, etc., to provide professional services and support for enterprises. Looking forward, the research directions can include: exploring the characteristics and requirements of entrepreneurship in the new era; comparative research across regions and industries; stimulating strategies for entrepreneurship in the digital age; and the relationship between entrepreneurship and social responsibility. These studies will help to deepen the understanding of entrepreneurship and provide more accurate guidance for policy making and practice. We look forward to the participation of more researchers and practitioners to jointly promote the healthy development of entrepreneurship.

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References

Zhong Qian. *Anhui is speeding up the building of "three regions and one area" with important influence* [N]. *Shanghai Securities News*, 2023-01-14 (004).

- Zhang Shuguang. *Give full play to the supporting role of measurement to accelerate the construction of "three places and one district" in Anhui province [J]. China Metrology, 2022, (10): 5-7.*
- Wang Wenjie, Liu Taigang. *Research on the influence of entrepreneurial environment on college students' entrepreneurial willingness —— Based on the survey analysis in Anhui Province [J]. Employment of Chinese College Students, 2023 (01): 40-45.*
- Li Tuyu. *China Coal Mine Construction Group: help the construction of "three places and one district" [J]. Decision-making, 2022, (05): 82-83.*
- Wu Shaolong. *Anhui capital market: service "three places and one district" construction to answer the registration system reform examination paper [N]. Securities Times, 2022-03-29 (A02).*
- Zhang Li, Li Rui. *Research on the optimization path of entrepreneurship education under the construction background of "Three Regions and one District" in Anhui Province [J]. Employment of Chinese College Students, 2022 (11): 45-49.*
- He Yi. *Enhance the service level and vitality of the capital market and boost the construction of "three places and one district" in Anhui province [J]. Tsinghua Financial Review, 2021, (11): 28-30. [8] Jin Lin. Anhui Industrial Fund "main force" serves the construction of "three regions and one region" [J]. Shanghai State Assets, 2021, (09): 38-40.*
- hao Ming, Zhang Yu. *Research on entrepreneurial Talent Training mode under the background of the construction of "Three Regions and one Region" in Anhui Province [J]. Human Resources Development in China, 2020,37 (11): 108-114.*
- Li Yanshuang, Xiao Yunna. *On the stimulation and protection of entrepreneurs' innovation and entrepreneurship spirit [J]. Accounting Monthly, 2020 (13): 6.*
- Wang Jingchao. *On the countermeasures to Stimulate and protect Entrepreneurship in the new Era [J]. Chiko, 2019,000 (022): 189.*